

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

D10.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

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1 Executive summary

The aim of the **INNO4CFIs project** “Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging Innovations to enhance Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs) while preserving Biodiversity, Water Security and Soil Health” - is to promote carbon farming and nature-based business models, technology and innovation to increase CO2 capturing while nurturing vital environmental benefits like freshwater production, soil restoration, and biodiversity enhancement. With a focus on carbon farming initiatives and reforestation, the objective is to develop a Carbon Technology Platform, redefine carbon farming and create a highly replicable and scalable business model in the Carbon Farming sector.

The aim is to develop a new way of carbon farming that captivates and reduces carbon emissions whilst contributing positively to the environment and rural communities which demonstrates a regenerative approach. Demonstrated in four living labs, INNO4CFIs is integrating highly innovative technologies including desalination-, mycelium-, satellite and space technologies and finances other green technologies by a cascade funding scheme to foster resilience and competitiveness in European regions. The INNO4CFIs consortium, led by Fondazione E. Amaldi, consists of 14 partners representing and promoting the innovation ecosystem of 13 different regions from 8 European countries (IT, GR, SP, BE, NL, IE, AT, DE). The project duration is 36 months with the aim to become a sustainable business after the project's lifetime.

For a coherent and effective implementation of WP10 Dissemination and Sustainability of the INNO4CFIs project, a detailed Dissemination and Communication plan has been developed at the beginning of the project (M3). This plan comprises the strategy for dissemination, communication and sustainability which are closely interrelated and go hand-in-hand. The strategy is based on profound stakeholder analysis and mapping with the consortium partners in M2, and describes how the project's results are disseminated and communicated via a broad range of communication channels, platforms and tools. Furthermore, a thorough sustainability strategy and stakeholder engagement plan defines the project's approach to ensure exploitation and market uptake by clustering, partnerships and the development of a sustainable business model. Continuous monitoring and evaluation ensure the adaptation to complex market environments and the resilience of INNO4CFIs. The Plan also covers the Visual Identity of the project and the key messages to address the key stakeholder groups.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan will be regularly updated and published in M12, M24 and M36.

2 Introduction

The Dissemination, communication and sustainability strategy of the project is key to reaching the project's objectives of fostering innovative ecosystems in European regions and developing a sustainable business model. The objective of the INNO4CFIs WP10 Dissemination and Sustainability is to:

- Raise awareness and increase the visibility of Carbon Farming solutions,
- Communicate effectively with key audiences,
- Involve, cooperate with and integrate views of stakeholders to ensure the sustainability of the project,
- Establish collaborations and a wide network to enable the scalability of the project,
- Promote supportive policy conditions for the project's exploitation opportunities that last beyond project lifetime.

The **Dissemination and Communication Plan** outlines the dissemination, communication and sustainability strategy and implementation plan. It elaborates on the stakeholder mapping and analysis, the external communication strategy to promote INNO4CFIs outcomes to the right stakeholders, the internal communication to enable optimal project results through internal collaboration, and the sustainability strategy which includes the stakeholder engagement strategy, clustering and partnerships, project network and market- and policy uptake. This document provides a clear overview of how all communication channels, activities and tools, stakeholder engagement activities and sustainability instruments work together to reach the project's objectives and foster innovation in European regions.

WP10 is a horizontal work package that bridges the results of the other work packages and a very good collaboration amongst project partners is needed for wide dissemination, communication and effective implementation of the sustainability strategy. For a successful implementation the full cooperation of the coordinator and the work package leaders as well as of all project partners' direct involvement is essential.

The work of WP10 includes three interrelated areas:

1. Communication
2. Dissemination
3. Sustainability

The objectives related to the internal and external **communication** of INNO4CFIs are:

- Developing a coherent project communication and website.
- Developing the communication plan including a visual identity.
- Developing a stakeholder analysis and mapping.
- Developing key messages and communicating effectively with target audiences.
- Developing and maintaining communication channels.
- To facilitate internal communication flows related to the dissemination, communication and sustainability of the project.
- Supporting partners in the dissemination and communication of the project.

The objectives related to the **dissemination** of INNO4CFIs are:

- Raising awareness and informing relevant stakeholders about the project's outcomes.
- Translating technical language to the needs of different target audiences to captivate their attention and engage them.
- Disseminating project results widely and effectively to a broad range of stakeholders via peer-reviewed articles, journal articles, scientific conferences and practitioner events.

The objectives related to the **sustainability** INNO4CFIs are:

- Developing coherent stakeholder mapping and engagement plan for the whole project, to ensure an effective outreach and engagement of stakeholders to reach INNO4CFIs objectives and develop a business model for the Carbon Technology platform.
- Conducting 3 interactive workshops to engage, and integrate relevant stakeholders' views.
- Developing a project network database that enables the coordination of the outreach to stakeholders in the 13 regions of the project and other regions of Europe.
- Developing a clustering strategy that leads to the signature of minimum 5 MoU's as stated in the Grant Agreement to ensure the continued scalability of the project beyond project lifetime.
- Contributing to the market uptake by facilitating the taskforce product and sustainability of the INNO4CFIs project.

This document outlines the strategy, implementation tools, KPIs and timeline to reach the above-mentioned objectives.

3 Dissemination & Communication Strategy and Implementation

3.1 Methodology

The dissemination and communication strategy plays an important role in collaborative research projects and for innovative projects with the aim to scale their innovations on the market, effective communication and stakeholder engagement are key for the sustainability of a project. The previously mentioned objectives regarding the dissemination, communication and sustainability of the project will be achieved by the following methodology and tasks:

- Task 10.1: Dissemination and communication activities
- Task 10.2: Clustering, stakeholder engagement and policy uptake

To implement these tasks, the following deliverables of INNO4CFIs WP10 will be developed:

- D10.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan: It will be developed, regularly updated and published at key dates during the project (M3, M12, M24, M36).
- D10.5: MoU and Lol signed with partners

The deliverables allow the coherent and continuous development and implementation of the tasks in WP10. It ensures that the project partners make progress in a timely and efficient manner.

Circonnect is the work package leader of WP10 Dissemination and Sustainability and coordinates the implementation of the tasks and activities. However, all partners will be involved in the activities undertaken in WP10 and responsible for the successful implementation of the dissemination and sustainability of the project. The following partners also play a crucial role in the dissemination, communication and sustainability: F6S, Planet, USAL, NTUA, FEA. The collaboration on this work package is crucial to ensure that the project results are disseminated in a high-quality manner, ensure widespread stakeholder engagement and coherent action to develop a sustainable business model for INNO4CFIs.

The dissemination and sustainability strategy is led by Circonnect and developed in a co-design process with inputs from all partners via co-design workshops, surveys, personal

conversations, and other tools. The dissemination and communication plan is a guiding document for all partners and has been developed in line with [“Communicating research for evidence-based policymaking. A practical guide for researchers in socio-economic sciences and humanities”](#) (European Commission, 2010), as well as with the most recent documents [“Communication, Dissemination and, Exploitation:–“Why they all matters and what is the difference?”](#) (EASME 2019, REA 2023).

The following activities will be undertaken:

1. Stakeholder analysis and Mapping
2. Definition of target audience and key messages
3. Developing the visual identity incl. brand manual and templates
4. Developing external communication activities for external representation of the project such as website, social media channels, newsletter, press releases, and communication material.
5. Dissemination of INNO4CFIs at scientific conferences, practitioner events, in scientific journals and magazines.
6. Developing and implementing the INNO4CFIs sustainability strategy. This includes the stakeholder engagement plan, interactive workshops, project network database, clustering strategy, market uptake, policy uptake.
7. Developing the concept of and coordinating the final conference.
8. Continuous monitoring and evaluation and adaptation of the dissemination and communication plan.

The activities of WP10 are to be discussed with partners on an ongoing basis, up-to-date information will be provided via meetings, email exchanges and shared platforms. The aim is that the WP leader coordinates the activities in a high-quality and effective manner and supports the partners in the dissemination and communication of the project. The partners communicate INNO4CFIs results as soon as they are public and relevant, engage stakeholders in an effective manner and provide updates to the WP leader to allow effective coordination and monitoring.

The project language is English. In order to ensure consistency, we recommend using British English spelling conventions and the language formalities elaborated in the [English Style Guide by the European Commission \(2023\)](#) where possible.

3.2 Stakeholder analysis & mapping

3.2.1 Approach of stakeholder analysis and mapping

The stakeholder analysis and mapping is the basis of the dissemination-, communication- and sustainability strategy. Stakeholder groups are groups of people who are impacted by the project. They will be involved and included in the stakeholder engagement and dissemination and communication activities. The aim is to develop an understanding of the stakeholder groups to define the stakeholder engagement of the whole INNO4CFIs project. Throughout the project stakeholders are addressed in different, yet complementary ways. In the context of WP10, a stakeholder mapping and analysis is being conducted with inputs from all partners.

The stakeholder mapping & analysis consists of five parts:

1. Stakeholder identification: Definition of stakeholder groups and target audiences
2. Stakeholder Analysis: A survey with the consortium partners was conducted to get an understanding how the stakeholder groups are related to the whole project and develop the stakeholder matrix.
3. Alignment on stakeholder engagement: A deeper understanding of the needs and strategies towards the stakeholders was identified and discussed in a workshop where also the existing connections within the prioritised stakeholder groups were identified.
4. Mapping the stakeholder groups to development of the stakeholder engagement strategy and instruments
5. Documentation of the approach as part of the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

For the project a wide range of stakeholders including local, regional and international as well as business, academia, media and politics are relevant. A survey and workshop about stakeholder mapping which has been conducted in M2 ensures to involve the expertise and network of all partners and develop a comprehensive and aligned basis for the stakeholder engagement. Based on this initial stakeholder analysis, a stakeholder matrix and the key strategies to engage these stakeholder groups (as outlined in Chapter 6) have been developed. Identifying individual stakeholders (companies and contact persons) from the stakeholder groups, based on the network of the consortium partners, has been started during the stakeholder workshop and will be carried on during the project. A system of

centralised (by the project) and decentralised (by stakeholders within their own network) stakeholder engagement is foreseen. After an initial understanding of the stakeholders and how to address them, INNO4CFIs pursues an agile approach to stakeholder engagement. This means continuous evaluation and adaptation will ensure effective stakeholder engagement.

3.2.2 Stakeholder identification

Categories of stakeholders

When identifying the stakeholders, three main perspectives have been looked at:

- **Institutional**: The regenerative Carbon Farming model needs to be integrated into the existing systems and supported by strong institutions. Therefore, policy makers and municipalities, associations, clusters, governance, media or networks supporting the uptake of the solutions provided by the consortium will be considered.
- **Economical**: To develop viable models for all actors in the value chain of Carbon Farming, the financial partners need to be identified. Investors, providers and buyers of carbon credits, farmers and related partners will be needed in order to set up systemic solutions.
- **Geographical**: Focus of the implementation of INNO4CFIs solutions are the 8 countries and 13 regions in which the consortium partners are located. In these countries the living labs will be implemented (planned in Italy, Spain, Greece and Belgium) and the policy makers will be addressed initially. The project strives to promote innovative solutions, therefore countries with a moderate innovative level are in the focus of the activities. For the wider engagement of stakeholders the focus is on European partners or on partners who are implementing solutions in Europe.

Grouping of stakeholders

To continuously promote the project, bring network partners on board and ensure the sustainability and uptake of the project results, various stakeholder groups need to be engaged by the project partners. The Stakeholder analysis covers 2 main aspects:

1. Stakeholder groups in the project development process
2. Stakeholder groups interested in the implementation and usage of INNO4CFIs products.

Part of the 2nd group of stakeholders will be identified during the work of the project, so it will be continuously updated during the project. In the context of WP10 an initial understanding and prioritisation is developed to focus the communication and dissemination activities and address the needs and concerns of these groups.

For both aspects, it is important to understand which stakeholders are already known and involved and which need to be addressed by the project partners.

By addressing these groups of stakeholders, the project will be promoted, communicated, disseminated, and further developed in a sustainable way.

Clusters of stakeholder groups

Throughout the stakeholder analysis and mapping INNO4CFIs has identified the following stakeholder groups that are relevant for the project. They can be categorised into three main clusters based on their role towards the uptake of the solutions as shown in the following table.

Enablers	Enabling the framework for sustainable and regenerative models of carbon farming	Policy makers on EU, national and regional level
		Municipalities
		Environmental agencies & NGOs
		Innovation & Technology Ecosystems
Implementers	Stakeholders to develop, implement and operate carbon farming solutions	Innovative SMEs (partners in setting up solutions)
		Companies / Carbon Credit Buyers
		Farmers and agricultural communities
		Investors
		Carbon Credit verifiers & brokers
Multipliers	Networks to spread the word about regenerative carbon farming, involving partners for collaboration	Business & Sustainability Clusters
		Green technology & environment clusters
		Universities and Research institutes
		I3 and other European programs and projects
		Media

Table 1: Clusters of stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Matrix

INNO4CFIs developed a stakeholder matrix based on the perceived interest of stakeholder groups in the project results and their influence in bringing those to the market.

The Influence-Interest matrix is used to understand how to address the stakeholder groups. There are four main areas of interest which can be differentiated. For each of these areas a key strategy by INNO4CFIs is defined and outlined in the figure below.

Figure 1: Strategies depending on Influence and Interest

How to apply these strategies will be shown in the stakeholder engagement strategy and planning.

- **Engage:** Stakeholders are crucial for the project success, therefore will be addressed with highest priority. Engagement can be via workshops, meetings, conferences and personal interaction of consortium partners. Individual stakeholders will be identified, and a detailed analysis of their needs to promote the INNO4CFIs solution will be developed.
- **Consult:** It is important to understand what is driving the implementation of INNO4CFIs solutions, therefore this group will be addressed when needed. Surveys or conversations with representatives from the groups will be used to gain a better understanding how the implementation can be promoted.
- **Collaborate:** Stakeholder groups which have a higher interest in developing the solutions or in applying it in their own environment are potential partners for collaboration. Based on the needs of the consortium to mature the solutions individual stakeholders from these groups will be contacted.

- Monitor: General information about the project can be used to address these groups, the effort of direct interaction will be kept low.

3.2.3 Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder survey

A [survey](#) has been conducted with the participation of 10 partners of the consortium. The aim of the survey and stakeholder workshop with the consortium partners was to get a common understanding about the needs to engage with stakeholders.

- Who are the stakeholder groups we want to focus on at a project level?
- How high is their interest in the project and in which parts of the project are they most interested in? What would provide value to them?
- How high is their importance and capacity to implement and promote INNO4CFIs solutions? With which activities can they increase the uptake of the solutions?
- What are the priorities when communicating and engaging the stakeholder groups?
- How are the consortium partners connected to these stakeholder groups or individual stakeholders?

The objective is to identify their relevance to the project, identifying target audiences and agreeing on how to collaborate to engage them. Engaging stakeholders is essential for the project and there are dedicated activities in various work packages (specifically WP2, WP7, WP9, WP10). The survey results were verified in the Stakeholder Workshop.

Stakeholder interests

Understanding why the stakeholder groups are interested in the project will help to engage them in the way which most serves their needs. INNO4CFIs will not only provide solutions for the Carbon Farming market but also a deeper understanding, opportunities to collaborate and develop business opportunities and the means to work on strategies for climate adaptation and a healthy environment.

The **main interests** of these groups are to get into contact with the consortium (collaboration & network as well as innovation & technology were seen as main fields of interest) as well as learning about the solutions, especially to understand how we will interact with the Carbon Credit system. An overview on the main interests is shown in the table below.

What INNO4CFIs provides	Which stakeholder groups are most interested?
Gaining Knowledge	Universities, Environmental Agencies, I3/European Programs, Policy makers
Collaboration & Network	Innovative SMEs, I3/European programs, Universities, Business Clusters, Environmental Agencies, Media
Carbon credits system	Carbon Credit Buyers, Investors, Carbon Credit verifiers & brokers
Carbon farming solutions	Carbon credit verifiers & brokers, Policy makers
Innovation & technology	Universities, Innovation & Technology Ecosystem, Business & Sustainability Clusters, Policy makers
Business opportunities	Investors, Farmers, Business & Sustainability Clusters, Innovative SMEs
Climate adaptation & healthy environment	Policy makers, Farmers, Environmental Agencies

Table 2: Interests of stakeholder groups in INNO4CFIs work

Stakeholders supporting the uptake of INNO4CFIs

There are five ways how the stakeholder groups can support the INNO4CFIs project and increase its market uptake. Access to policy makers, potential users and funding / financial resources will ensure that the solutions are accepted on the market. Engaging the own network to establish sustainable solutions and using the own communication channels to talk about the solutions will ensure a wider understanding about the solutions. The 2 groups can be characterised as

1. Key partners for exploitation and market uptake
2. Key partners to spread the ideas

Key partners for exploitation and market uptake
 These are the groups with a **higher influence on the market uptake due to their access to policy implementation, financial resources & funding as well as potential users.** They

should be engaged and consulted as they will speed up the implementation of the INNO4CFIs solutions.

The attached diagram shows the potential evaluated by the consortium partners in the survey. The groups highlighted in green are seen as the ones with the highest potential to access the decision makers. The stakeholders highlighted in blue are seen with medium potential, too.

Figure 2: Key stakeholder groups for exploitation and market uptake

A strong connection to the market will need to be built up as part of WP7 when developing the business models.

Key partners to spread the ideas

Which stakeholder groups are perceived to have the best reach to distribute the solutions via their communication channels? This question was answered during the survey, and individual partners have been identified in the stakeholder workshop.

Figure 3: Stakeholder groups with networks and communication channels

As they are also having partners in their networks which can help to further develop the technology and innovative solutions with the partners of INNO4CFIs the strategies of collaboration and information will be applied to ensure especially the groups shown in green in the attached diagram will be addressed in a good way.

The focus will be to provide information to the groups so that they can share and identify the individual stakeholders within the Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Universities, Environmental agencies, and Media who have the highest reach and widest networks to increase the effect.

During the stakeholder workshop further contacts to the stakeholder groups were identified, those will be collected continuously during the project in the Project Network Database.

3.2.4 Stakeholder Mapping

The analysis has been refined based on the survey results and the discussion in the workshop. 20 participants from 12 partners of the consortium partners participated in a stakeholder workshop which was used to show the survey result and discuss action points based on these.

INNO4CFIs stakeholder matrix

Based on the results of the survey it becomes obvious that most of the stakeholder groups identified upfront are seen as key partners to ensure market uptake of INNO4CFIs solutions. Most of the groups are seen in the ENGAGE section of the matrix, which means that spending

time and effort on communication, networking and personal interaction with these stakeholder groups is needed.

The **most important stakeholder groups** to ensure the uptake of regenerative Carbon Farming models are the Policy makers on European, national and regional level as well as the market participants of the carbon credit market. Innovation & Technology Ecosystems as well as business clusters and other European programs were identified as further key stakeholders to be addressed and targeted for the communication.

Figure 4: Stakeholder matrix of INNO4CFIs

Main strategies to address the stakeholders:

Even if the stakeholders have been mapped into the same area, the main actions to Engage, Collaborate and Consult can differ based on the background of each group. The main actions will be further elaborated in the next sections.

Strategy	Partners	Key Actions
Engage	Carbon Credit Verifiers & Buyers	Understand the systems, Identify & contact potential partners, get feedback on solutions

Engage	Policy makers on different levels	Advocacy to raise requirements to Carbon Farming solutions
Engage	I3 & other European programmes, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Business & Sustainability Cluster	Actively seek exchange of ideas, invite to networking events, Promote I3 instruments and Technology partners
Collaborate	Environmental Agencies & NGOs, Universities & Research Institutes	Identify opportunities to work with individual partners
Collaborate	Investors	Identify impact investors for innovative solutions
Consult	Farmers, Media	Identify channels to increase visibility
Consult	Innovative SMEs	Gain Know-how for technology partners, Apply technology
Monitor	Municipalities	Provide information to municipalities where living labs are located

Table 3: Key stakeholder strategies for INNO4CFIs stakeholder groups

Stakeholder groups for exploitation

Based on the analysis of the market uptake, the INNO4CFIs consortium identified the following stakeholder groups as relevant to promote the market uptake in the following ways via the Stakeholder Survey, as described in the table:

Uptake of INNO4CFIs solutions by	Which are the key stakeholders?
Access to policy implementation	Policy makers, Municipalities, I3 & European programs
Access to potential users	Business & Sustainability clusters, Carbon Credit verifiers & brokers, Farmers and agricultural communities, Companies / Carbon Credit buyers
Access to funding / financial resources	Investors, Business & Sustainability clusters, Innovative SMEs
Establishing sustainable solutions within the network	Universities, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Business & Sustainability Clusters, Environmental Agencies & NGOs, Innovative SMEs
Dissemination within the own communication channels	Media, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Policy makers, Environmental Agencies & NGOs, Universities, Innovative SMEs, Business & Sustainability Clusters

Table 4: Stakeholder groups to be addressed for uptake of the solutions

For engaging stakeholders in an effective way INNO4CFIs developed a Stakeholder engagement strategy and tools elaborated in chapter 6.

3.2.5 Target audience

During the stakeholder analysis and mapping the following target audiences have been identified. The target audiences are the groups of people who should know about the project, engage with INNO4CFIs and follow specific Call-To-Actions. Effective engagement with the right audiences is of paramount importance for the success of an innovation action project. It impacts the project's success and also influences the adoption and utilisation of research outcomes. To achieve an effective dissemination and communication strategy, it is imperative to pinpoint the precise target audiences and employ appropriate channels and communication tools.

The following six target audiences will be addressed in the communication and dissemination activities:

- Policy makers on EU, national and regional level
- Innovative SMEs (Green tech & carbon farming)

- Investors
- Farmers and agricultural community
- Carbon Credit buyers
- Media

This meticulous classification ensures that INNO4CFIs's outreach is tailored to the specific needs and expectations of each group, thereby optimising the dissemination and communication strategy.

3.3 Key messages

Based on the stakeholder analysis, the needs of the target audiences, INNO4CFIs has defined the key messages and chosen a tone of voice to convey the messages in an attractive and engaging way to the target audiences. The INNO4CFIs communication and dissemination includes one-way, two-way and network communication:

- One-way communication: The receiver listens and reads the communication, but does not respond. INNO4CFIs aims to share knowledge and increase awareness about the topics related to carbon farming.
- Two-way interaction: The receiver sends feedback to the sender of the message. An interaction occurs which will then be integrated into the INNO4CFIs development. This is a key aim of the communication efforts of INNO4CFIs.
- Network communication: The receivers share the message with their networks. That way the communication is spread widely. INNO4CFIs will foster network communication by developing good partnerships with key stakeholders that will be invited to share the key messages.

3.3.1 Tone of voice

The INNO4CFIs project adopts a unique tone of voice that combines **professionalism with infotainment**, all while keeping the project's objectives at the forefront of communication. It presents the facts in a clear way, while also ensuring that messaging is accessible and engaging to a diverse audience.

Professionalism:

The dedication to professionalism is the backbone of the INNO4CFIs project. The project addresses the pressing issues of carbon farming, reforestation, and the environment with the utmost seriousness. The consortium of experts and the wealth of scientific research

behind the work ensure that it upholds the highest standards of integrity, transparency, and credibility. The professionalism ensures that the potential stakeholders and partners can rely on the project for accurate, data-driven information and expert insights.

Infotainment:

While the mission is rooted in science and sustainable practices, the importance of engaging and informing a broad audience is understood. INNO4CFIs embraces the concept of "infotainment" to make complex topics accessible and captivating. It is strived to turn data into stories, to entertain as educate, and to inspire action through compelling narratives and visuals. The ultimate goal is to excite and engage a diverse audience, fostering understanding and enthusiasm.

3.3.2 Key messages for individual stakeholder groups

Defining the key messages is important, because they are the basis of the communication of INNO4CFIs and addressing the target audiences. INNO4CFIs is developing the following key messages for the target audiences in a three-step approach.

- **Co-design workshop at the Kick-off meeting in September 2023:** The partners collected key messages and identified the importance of the messages for the target audiences. The integration of all partners in this process ensured that this ambitious and multi-faceted project INNO4CFIs is communicated in an effective way.
- **Analysis and Development of key message:** Circonnect has developed and summarised the key messages for the target audiences with inputs from partners.
- **Evaluation and adaptation:** Since INNO4CFIs will develop as a project, product, platform and business throughout the three years, there might be the need to adapt the key messages. Therefore the key messages will be evaluated regularly and adapted when needed.

The following chapters show the key messages for the target audiences.

Policy makers on EU, national and regional level:

For the effective communication and dissemination to policy makers, it is essential to be aware and address the existing policy frameworks. On EU-level these include the [Farm2Fork Strategy](#), [Green Deal](#), [Carbon Removal Certification](#) or [Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\)](#), [EU Soil strategy for 2030](#), [EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#). The policy gaps for a successful

implementation of INNO4CFIs and how to address them will be developed throughout the project.

The communication objective when communicating with European authorities and policy makers is to actively involve them in the process of delivering concise and influential messages to top-tier stakeholders and decision-makers. The aim is to expedite meaningful changes in the policy framework in the realm of regenerative and positive impact carbon farming management and associated legislative matters.

The fundamental message directed at this influential group should be compelling, carrying a distinct political undertone, and, once again, feature a lucid call to action. It is paramount that this message prompts them to take decisive action and lead the charge in effecting the necessary transformations for the domains of nature based solutions, create positive impact to regenerate the environment, non-conventional agricultural management and relevant legislation.

Key messages:

- *“INNO4CFIs provides data-driven solutions to address climate change. Support it by aligning policy frameworks and goals.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs offers actionable insights and sustainable practices to inform and shape carbon farming legislation. Access our resources and networks to influence policy decisions, shape corporate sustainability practices, and make a lasting difference.”*
- *“Collaborate with us to multiply your positive impact on the business models for climate, environment and biodiversity. INNO4CFIs offers a unique opportunity to foster European resilience, business opportunities and climate and environmental solutions driven by SMEs in 13 European regions.”*

The communication objective when reaching out to national governments and policymakers is both to increase awareness of the project as well as to inspire their active involvement, effectively making them advocates for the project's cause.

The pivotal message directed towards this group must be straightforward, optimistic, and compelling, incorporating a clear call to action. The language used should steer clear of technical jargon and instead infuse an emotional appeal tailored to the specific interests of this target audience. Through this message, it should be made evident that they can identify themselves as integral contributors to solutions within their local jurisdictions and on a broader scale.

Key messages:

- *“Support the implementation of carbon farming solutions with a positive impact on climate adaptation, water usage, biodiversity and soil quality. INNO4CFIs showcases solutions on local and regional levels.*
- *“Partner with us to develop sustainable policies and initiatives for regenerative carbon farming that benefit your region, community and environment. INNO4CFIs project provides actionable solutions to address local environmental challenges while promoting economic sustainability.”*
- *“Join a network of forward-thinking innovators, SMEs and policymakers committed to making a positive impact on the environment and their residents' quality of life.”*

Innovative SMEs

Another pivotal target audience comprises innovative SMEs in the field of green technologies, that are vital partners in shaping and implementing solutions. From the project's inception, it is sought to actively involve them in the project's endeavours, fostering collaborative efforts and mutual growth. Especially the call for proposals for the cascade funding will be directed to them.

INNO4CFIs communication strategy underscores a forward-looking approach that centres on innovation, collaboration, and collective success. The key message should radiate enthusiasm, underscore the prospects of mutual benefit, and encourage the SMEs to join hands in shaping a dynamic future that unlocks new possibilities.

Key messages:

- *“INNO4CFIs is a Carbon Technology platform for cutting-edge innovation in the fields of green technologies for regenerative carbon farming. Join our network of experts to advance your innovations.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs is dedicated to sharing knowledge and fostering scientific innovation. The project provides a collaborative ecosystem where your innovative solutions can gain real-world traction.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs offers opportunities for networking, funding, and collaboration. Leverage the business model of your green-tech SME to grow while contributing to environmental sustainability.*

- *“Are you an innovative SME with green solutions? Collaborate with us to expand your knowledge about business models for carbon farming, your reach and impact. Join the Carbon Farming Technology Platform “INNO4CFIs” and promote innovative carbon farming solutions across Europe.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs offers a platform for showcasing business models and green technologies. Access our network and resources to take your innovative solutions to the next level, to drive sustainability while boosting your business.”*

Investors

The primary focus lies on engaging various investor groups, which encompass impact investors and public funding representatives, as one of the central target audiences right from the outset of the project's implementation. The objective is twofold: to cultivate awareness and to nurture the potential for collaborations and co-financing of the project.

Within the communication strategy, the emphasis is a triple-bottom-line approach, embracing economic, environmental, and social impacts. The core message should exude dynamism, radiate positivity, and be profoundly persuasive, all while anchoring its essence in the long-term vision that INNO4CFIs is poised to deliver.

Key messages:

- *“Invest in green innovation and business opportunities in carbon farming and reforestation to reliably offset your carbon footprint and achieve sustainability goals. Partner with us to have a positive impact on all levels - economic, environment and quality of life.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs offers green-tech solutions that drive resilience for European citizens by promoting the economy, positively impacting the environment and creating climate solutions. Invest in sustainable solutions with proven environmental and financial benefits.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs offers opportunities for growth in the green-tech sector, supporting your commitment to a cleaner future. Partner with us to drive innovation and sustainable profitability in the realm of carbon farming and reforestation.”*
- *“Join INNO4CFIs community of businesses committed to reducing their carbon footprint and contributing to global SDGs. Promote business models that foster climate solutions with a positive impact on the environment.”*

- *“Invest in solutions for a sustainable and regenerative future - promote reliably tracked carbon farming actions which capture carbon, nurture the soil and provide biodiversity. Get access to highly valuable carbon credits at an early stage”.*

Farmers and agricultural community:

At the heart of the INNO4CFIs mission are farmers and the broader agricultural community. Their participation is central to the success of the project. The project is committed to engaging them from the outset to ensure that their perspectives and needs are fully considered.

In the communication strategy, it is prioritised a message that resonates with the values and aspirations of the farming community. The key message should be down-to-earth, highlighting the tangible benefits of INNO4CFIs, and, most importantly, inspire them to see themselves as integral contributors to a more sustainable and prosperous agricultural landscape.

Key messages:

- *“Discover eco-friendly farming practices that have a positive impact on soil and biodiversity and by that improve your crop yield and profitability. Join us and leverage your farming practices and expertise by access to resources and networking.”*
- *“INNO4CFIs offers knowledge, resources, expertise, and support to transition to sustainable and profitable carbon farming methods. Join a community of like-minded farmers committed to environmental stewardship and financial success.”*
- *“Develop and diversify your impact for the future by adding resilient carbon farming solutions to your portfolio of services to ensure fair payment for your services to the community.”*

Carbon credit buyers:

Carbon credit buyers, which are often companies and organisations with sustainability commitments, are a significant audience. By emphasising the transparency of the verification processes, the business benefits of carbon credit investments, and the tangible environmental impact, INNO4CFIs targets corporate buyers who aim to offset their carbon

footprint while enhancing their corporate social responsibility and brand reputation. These tailored strategies are intended to engage this critical audience segment, supporting their environmental goals while contributing to the projects. As recent issues on the voluntary carbon market have created scepticism if the credits fulfil the promises, the regenerative Carbon Farming with providing tracking options to verify the performance can show a way forward and reduce the risk of not accepted offsets. This should be brought across in the messaging.

For individuals interested in carbon credit investments, INNO4CFIs provides an opportunity to offset their personal carbon footprint and support environmental conservation. The messaging is tailored to highlight how purchasing carbon credits aligns with their values and offers a direct and measurable contribution to carbon reduction, reforestation, and biodiversity enhancement. This approach targets eco-conscious individuals looking to make a positive impact on the environment.

Key messages:

- *“Connect with us to explore opportunities for verified carbon credits that support environmental sustainability. We offer reliable data, expertise, and partnerships to ensure your carbon credit investments make a real difference.”*
- *“Let's work together to create a cleaner future and navigate the complex world of carbon credit verification and trading. Embrace sustainability and corporate responsibility by purchasing carbon credits from our project.”*
- *“Make a tangible impact on carbon reduction, reforestation, and biodiversity enhancement. Invest in our verified carbon credits to reduce your carbon footprint while enhancing your brand reputation.”*

Media:

The approach to media engagement is designed to resonate with media representatives who seek compelling stories and credible sources. By offering captivating narratives, data-driven content, expert interviews (in the second half of the project), it is aimed to capture the interest of journalists, reporters, and influencers. Through these efforts, it can be ensured that the mission of INNO4CFIs is communicated effectively to a wider audience, while providing the media with the content they need to inform and inspire their readers, viewers, and listeners. Doubts to the current carbon credit systems should be actively addressed explaining the verifiable and credible solutions.

Key messages:

- *“Discover captivating stories and transformative impact as we work towards a greener future. Our project is your trusted source for inspiring and credible environmental solutions. Engage with experts and uncover transformative narratives in carbon farming and sustainability.”*
- *“Access our team for in-depth information and interviews to share the message with a broader audience on the innovative solutions of the so-called carbon farming”.*
- *“Covering the latest trends in environmental innovation? Our project is at the forefront of green tech and carbon farming initiatives. Access reliable data, expert insights, and exclusive content for informed and impactful reporting.”*
- *“Carbon farming beyond a single carbon capture perspective. Discover how the reduction of carbon from the atmosphere can be combined with technologies providing benefits for biodiversity, restore and nurture the soils and deal with water scarcity”.*

3.4 Visual identity & tools

3.4.1 Visual identity

The project's visual identity is designed to express the essence of the project in a visual way, distinguishing INNO4CFIs while leaving a memorable mark. It encompasses the creation of a unique logo, the name, an iconic symbol, and an impactful slogan. The logo, acting as the project's visual ambassador, will feature prominently in all communication materials, making it a key element of recognition. The slogan, whether referred to as a motto, strapline, or tagline, can take the form of a concise three-word formula or a succinct call to action, encapsulating the project's objectives and values.

Keywords of the visual character:

The following words express the character of the brand INNO4CFIs and are reflected in the visual identity:

- Sustainable, circular & regenerative
- Innovative
- Integrative

- Collaborative
- Solution-oriented
- Regional
- Regenerative
- Alive
- Dynamic

Official Name and full title of the project:

*Nature-Based Business Model and Emerging **Innovations** to enhance **Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs)** while preserving Biodiversity, Water Security and Soil Health*

This title will be highlighted on main communication channels and in official documents such as the website and on social media channels if the space allows it.

Short Name:

INNO4CFIs

The short name will be used in all communication and is the key recognition element of the project.

Logo:

Every project requires a strong, evocative, and memorable logo which is a key element of the visual identity. By highly attuning to the essence of the project INNO4CFIs developed a logo that represents the story of the project. The main logo in blue-green and a secondary logo in white with a green background have been chosen by the consortium.

Figure 5: INNO4CFIs Logos

The INNO4CFIs logo's basic form is a circle, which represents the circular, integrative and collaborative approach as well as the Earth itself. The division into two segments stands for the symbiosis between technology and nature. It also represents a flow of water or data representing movement and progress. Although both forms are in motion, they are also in balance - complementing each other. United they complete a cycle and circulation.

The four surrounding circles represent the technologies that enable and accompany the green economic transformation and regenerative and sustainable approach to carbon farming.

Colours

The colour scheme chosen comprises the following four colours.

Main colours:

These colours are the basic colours used in all communication materials and tools.

- **Blue:** Technology, Clarity, Freedom and Depth
- **Green:** Nature, Growth, Hope, Departure

Additional colours:

These colours are used additionally to the main colours for highlights, visual accents and graphical designs.

- **Magenta:** Dynamic, Engagement and Alive
- **Yellow:** Mind, Innovation, Truth, Rationality, Optimism and New Ideas

Tagline:

The tagline is especially important for the brand and recognition value of the project, because the short name INNO4CFIs is not self-explanatory.

"**Regenerative Carbon Farming**" encapsulates INNO4CFIs's commitment to sustainable agriculture practices that not only mitigate carbon emissions but actively regenerates the environment by the positive impact on soil health, water supply and biodiversity. It symbolises the project's mission to foster the growth of carbon-absorbing ecosystems and business model, working in harmony with nature to restore and heal the planet while providing sustainable agricultural solutions.

Visual identity Guidelines:

The **Brand Manual** is the cornerstone of brand identity management. It serves as a comprehensive reference tool, outlining the visual, verbal, and experiential elements that define a brand. This manual provides clear instructions on how to consistently use brand assets such as logos, colours, placement, typography, graphical assets and imagery to maintain brand cohesiveness across all communication channels. It ensures that every interaction with the brand reflects its values and personality, fostering brand recognition and trust among audiences while safeguarding its integrity and consistency. **See the Brand Manual document in the Annex for more details.**

Additional to the guidelines in the brand manual, the guidelines highlighted in the G.A. to ensure the visibility of the funding statement are applicable on every communication material. On all publications and communication material (e.g. leaflet, report, website, posters etc.) the EU emblem and funding statement is demonstrated in one of the following ways. On social media posts the EU emblem including the statement "co-funded by the European Union" is used.

Short version:

Co-funded by
the European Union

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming - G.A. 101115156

Long version:

The INNO4CFIs project has received funding from the European Commission under the European Regional Development Fund I3 programme, Grant Agreement no. 101115156.

3.4.2 Communication templates

Aligned with the project's visual identity, a range of templates and dissemination materials have been crafted. These templates encompass a **PowerPoint presentation slide template**, a **Word Doc template**, a **Report template**, and an **e-mail banner (see Annex)**. The communication package is accessible on the shared Google Drive to assist partners in tailoring letters, presentations, or reports. All templates will be meticulously developed in strict adherence to the guidelines and regulations governing communication for projects funded by the European Commission, incorporating the disclaimers.

The introduction of the visual identity and templates is scheduled for presentation during M3. The Success story template's release falls within the timeframe spanning from M24 to M30, with the exact timing yet to be determined.

4 External dissemination and communication activities

The Dissemination and communication plan distinguishes between the following activities which are clearly defined by the European Commission in the document “Communication, dissemination and exploitation - Why they all matter and what is the difference” ([EASME 2019, REA 2023](#)). INNO4CFIs aligned the planning of communication, dissemination of the project with these definitions:

- **Communication:** The purpose is to inform, communicate, promote the results and engage stakeholders via the right strategy, key messages in communication channels.
- **Dissemination:** The purpose is to provide results and outcomes to stakeholders in scientific journals, conferences and open science platforms. The aim is to engage especially (but not only) the community of researchers and policymakers.

In the following chapters INNO4CFIs activities for communication and dissemination are outlined.

4.1 Communication activities

External communication serves as a crucial conduit for realising the INNO4CFIs project's overarching objectives, which include:

- Enhancing the visibility of Carbon Farming solutions.
- Facilitating effective communication with key audiences.
- Engaging stakeholders and nurturing an ecosystem to ensure the project's long-term sustainability.

- Establishing collaborations and fostering a wide-reaching network that endures well beyond the project's duration.

The dissemination and communication strategy is meticulously crafted to ensure comprehensive multi-stakeholder information and engagement. It is designed to achieve the following:

- Raise awareness about carbon farming solutions.
- Facilitate the transfer of knowledge and promote widespread acceptance.
- Encourage the adoption of **INNO4CFIs Carbon Technology Platform's** technology and business model.

To accomplish these ambitious goals, a variety of communication tools and channels, including the INNO4CFIs website, social media channels, media kits, policy briefs, newsletters, publications, and press articles, will be employed. It's important to note that some external communication materials will be distributed both digitally and in print format, with leaflets available in both formats.

4.1.1 Website

The project's website with the URL www.inno4cfis.eu will be the primary communication platform for introducing the project, showcasing its results, deliverables and progress, highlighting the consortium, and presenting updates about the project and regenerative carbon farming in the format of a blog. It will provide access to comprehensive project information to the public. The initial version of the website will go live by M6.

The INNO4CFIs website will feature a project summary, the project's objectives, the activities, the communication materials, policy briefs, its impact, the innovative approaches it employs, and public deliverables. Furthermore, there will be dedicated sections to promote the progress and results of the living labs, present the chosen green tech- providers who will be supported by the cascade funding, share INNO4CFIs news and events, and profile the project partners. It is also planned to create a dedicated section to the website, which will showcase the progress in the living labs in the format of the campaign "Tree Diary" (see in Chapter 4.1.3). It aims to highlight the progress of one tree in each living lab, personifying them with names. This approach underscores the long-term impact of the trees beyond the project's duration and underscores the importance of sustainability, climate action, and environmental efforts.

The website will be visually aligned with the INNO4CFIs brand, ensuring that visitors receive comprehensive information about the project and its activities. Additionally, it will offer a subscription form for the e-newsletter and provide contact information for inquiries and engagement. The overarching goal is to establish a robust online presence that facilitates effective communication and information dissemination to diverse stakeholders.

The website will be designed to achieve two primary objectives:

- Serve as the central information hub for INNO4CFIs, providing a comprehensive resource for explaining the project's objectives, offering the latest news updates, facilitating document downloads, and displaying social media content related to the project.
- Function as a broader platform for research in areas pertinent to INNO4CFIs, delivering crucial updates on external policy and research advancements that are relevant or influential to the project.

The key performance indicators for this project include achieving more than 1000 unique visitors to the website and securing over 20 references on other web pages, reflecting the project's significant online presence and impact.

4.1.2 Social media

INNO4CFIs is represented on the social media platforms LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube to share information and engage with relevant stakeholders. The different platforms also provide the opportunity to ensure that the project's campaigns reach a wide range of target groups in the long term. For instance, the "Tree Diary" campaign which will feature individual trees in each living lab, giving them names and showcasing their development.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is connecting people in the world of business. This will be the main communication channel to reach target audiences. A project LinkedIn page has been developed (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/inno4cfis-project/>) in M2 and it already has more than 120 followers. LinkedIn is a broadly used platform of the INNO4CFIs partners. Partners will share updates of the project via their networks on an individual basis via their personal LinkedIn page and via their company pages.

In terms of social media metrics, the key performance indicators for LinkedIn encompass gaining a follower base exceeding 500, alongside consistently garnering over 100 views per post.

Twitter/X

Twitter/X plays a pivotal role in a communication strategy by offering a real-time platform for rapid information dissemination and engagement with a diverse audience focusing on policymakers and media. Its concise and dynamic nature makes it ideal for sharing updates, sparking conversations, and connecting with stakeholders in a fast-paced digital environment. A twitter account for INNO4CFIs has already been developed (<https://twitter.com/INNO4CFIs>) and launched in M2.

On Twitter/X, the established key performance indicators include posting more than 150 tweets and consistently achieving over 100 views per post, signifying active engagement and reach across both platforms.

YouTube

YouTube will be used to upload the General Project video that will be created for INNO4CFIs as well as potential other videos that will be created in conferences, events, demo sites visits, interviews etc. The sharing of videos developed from site visits and other partner content will be promoted on the YouTube playlist for partners to share via their respective social media channels that can also be included on other relevant social accounts such as LinkedIn, and Twitter broadening the scope of outreach. An INNO4CFIs YouTube channel will be developed with the release of the first video.

Hashtags

For the effective communication, reach, searching efficiency and branding of SM's campaigns, hashtags need to be used. The INNO4CFIs hashtag which is already used is #INNO4CFIs. Other important hashtags are: #13instrument #carbonfarming #climateaction #sustainability #innovation #greentech #naturebasedsolutions #EUinnovation #ERDF #circulareconomy #climatesolution

4.1.3 Campaigns

The future campaigns encompass a series of initiatives designed to raise awareness, inspire action, and communicate the core messages of the project. Each campaign is strategically crafted to achieve specific objectives, whether it's introducing INNO4CFIs to a broader audience, spotlighting the people driving the project, showcasing compelling images and quotes, and technological solutions. These campaigns will collectively create a vibrant and multifaceted narrative that resonates with the stakeholders and underscores the project's significance and impact.

Upcoming campaigns:

- ***We are INNO4CFIs Project:*** A social media campaign will be employed to spotlight the individuals driving the INNO4CFIs project, sharing their motivation for the project in a quote, their role, stories, and contributions to foster a deeper connection with the audience.
- ***Tree Diary:*** The "Tree Diary" campaign will showcase one tree per living lab as a persona (including a name). It will show the progress of the tree and the activities in the living lab. The personification of trees as champions shows the long-term impact beyond the project lifetime and emphasises the significance of fostering

sustainability and climate and environmental actions. This campaign will be highlighted on social media and on the website.

4.1.4 Press release

INNO4CFIs plans to send two press releases in a carefully timed approach to disseminate key project updates to a wide-ranging audience. The first press release will be sent in M6 alongside the launch of the website, promoting the project launch to capture early attention from national, EU, and international media. Additionally, it is planned to issue press releases, later in the project, focusing on topics such as Cascade funding or towards the project's conclusion, unveiling the noteworthy results. The exact timing will be decided amongst consortium members and integrated in the updated deliverable. These press releases will serve as powerful tools to communicate the achievements, milestones, and contributions to a broader audience, ensuring the project's impactful narrative is heard on both the national and global stages.

4.1.5 Media relations

Media plays a pivotal role in amplifying the message and reaching the target audience and the interested public, thereby enhancing awareness not only of the INNO4CFIs project but also its findings, outcomes, and guidance. As an integral component of the project's communication strategy, Circonnect is proactively involving journalists and securing media coverage throughout the project's lifecycle. This will be achieved through a range of channels, social media content, news stories, and press releases. Additionally, the INNO4CFIs consortium is establishing a media contacts database, enabling the communication team to directly engage with representatives from various news platforms. This approach allows for the dissemination of project results and the establishment of both short-term and long-term media partnerships, tailored to the project's specific needs and stage. Furthermore, as it is aimed to widely disseminate INNO4CFIs policy briefs, media contacts from the database will be approached to pique their interest in the project's insights and recommendations for sharing on news portals. The engagement of media contacts is of utmost importance, as news stories backed by data and evidence-based facts often serve as a crucial source of information for policy makers.

4.1.6 Communication material

By M5, all communication materials will be developed, including a leaflet and a roll-up designed for both dissemination and promotional purposes. Posters will be developed on request as various conferences require different formats and content. These materials will serve to brand the project at both internal and external events. Should any additional poster or design requirements arise, WP10 will provide the necessary support. Furthermore, e-mail banners to promote INNO4CFIs effectively throughout the partner's networks in a digital way. The INNO4CFIs standard presentation serves as a tool to present the project at conferences.

The INNO4CFIs leaflet, a pivotal component of the communication strategy, will be distributed to all partners for dissemination and promotion during external conferences, meetings, or seminars. Additionally, it will be made readily accessible for download via the project's website, ensuring broad and convenient access to project information.

4.1.7 Newsletters

To keep stakeholders continuously informed, **six newsletters** will be circulated (in M6, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36), offering a concise and accessible means of sharing updates and highlights. Newsletters (e-newsletters) are publications that are regularly developed and distributed from the organisation to the list of people that have subscribed to receive the organisation's news. E - newsletters (via Mailchimp and LinkedIn) will be developed for INNO4CFIs and will be sent on a regular basis to the subscribers. These will be subscribers through the website, the LinkedIn page, through events and more. The e-newsletters will include news about the project, events that will take place or have taken place, publications relevant to the project and more and will be accompanied by pictures and relevant links to the website or other websites when necessary. The e-newsletters will be short (2-3 pages) and will have a specific format and layout, containing the logos of the project and the EU. All e-newsletters will be produced in English.

The e-newsletters are excellent means of communicating information regarding the INNO4CFIs project and facilitate communication with the target groups and stakeholders, both during and after the project's actions. Circonnact will do the preparation and distribution of the e-newsletter. In all the e-newsletters that will be sent the recipients shall have the option to unsubscribe from the receiving notifications regarding the project.

4.1.8 Videos

It is set to create a General Project video with a specific objective in mind: to provide a comprehensive overview of the project between M10 and M14. The video will serve as a powerful tool to raise awareness and enhance understanding of the INNO4CFIs project. To effectively convey the project's essence, the video will incorporate visual elements, showcasing technologies and living labs in action. Additionally, throughout the project's duration, videos will be captured during project-related meetings or other gatherings as needed, ensuring a dynamic and engaging means of communication for the stakeholders and the broader audience.

4.1.9 Interactive final event

To communicate and disseminate the final results and outcomes of the project a final event will be organised. The event will take place between M32 and M36. The event will take place in the context of a relevant conference or summit in the field of carbon farming/environment/ climate/ circular economy/ regenerative agriculture. The aim of the final event is to foster strong relationships and partnerships with key stakeholders and existing and potential clustering partners and disseminate the results and outcomes to the target audience. The event will be developed in an interactive way to share information in an effective way, ensure stakeholder engagement and attract interest of target audiences.

Other options to cross-promote the final event are the UN World Environment Day on 5 June or UN World Biodiversity Day on 22 May. The detailed planning of the final event will start in M20-M22 and will be included in the update of the Communication plan in M24.

4.2 Dissemination activities

INNO4CFIs pursues a multifaceted approach to disseminate the project's results and insights. It includes sharing results with the scientific community and policy makers via international and national scientific conferences and research papers published in scientific journals. Furthermore, INNO4CFIs has a special emphasis on disseminating the results at practitioner events and in magazines and journals in order to provide the results to the key stakeholders such as carbon credit buyers, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Business & Sustainability clusters, innovative SMEs and media. This is essential to promote the market uptake and engage individual stakeholders.

By the end of the project, a comprehensive Inventory of the success cases and go-to-business scenario (D2.7) will be released, as well as a guideline for stakeholders related to the INNO4CFIs carbon farming business model (D6.4).

The list of planned dissemination activities of each partner will be shown in Annex 2. It has been captured at M3 and will be updated in the forthcoming versions of the dissemination plan. As there is a high dynamic of the Carbon Farming market the consortium will continuously watch out at events, conferences or further opportunities to communicate about the regenerative Carbon Farming models and identify how to integrate them on the Carbon Credit 's markets.

Dissemination will occur in the following channels and forms by INNO4CFIs partners. This is an indicative planning foreseen in M3, it can be adapted due to the results, partnerships, and relevant topics in the industry.

4.2.1 Articles

To ensure a robust and well-rounded dissemination, INNO4CFIs aims to publish up to three scientific papers, amplifying the project's academic impact. Furthermore, the project partners plan to disseminate a minimum of six articles to non-academic magazines, thereby reaching a broader audience and enhancing the visibility of the project.

The following scientific papers are planned. They can be adapted due to results or progress of the project:

Partner	Topics to be disseminated	Key stakeholder groups and networks	Means of dissemination	Indicative timeframe
National Technical University of Athens	WEFE and WEFC nexus	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	Energy Nexus , Sustainability , Water-Energy-Nexus , Nexus	M18-M36
CNR	Carbon Farming in areas affected salt wedge; allometric equations in agroforestry	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	Scientific papers published in international journal	M24-36
USAL	Blockchain & AI for carbon farming	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence (DCAI), compiled in Springer proceedings	M10
USAL	Blockchain & AI for carbon farming	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence (DCAI), compiled in Springer proceedings	M10
USAL	How blockchain & AI promotes regenerative practices	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence (DCAI), compiled in Springer proceedings	M22

USAL	How blockchain & AI promotes regenerative practices	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence (DCAI), compiled in Springer proceedings	M22
USAL	Using AI & Blockchain to verify carbon credits	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence (DCAI), compiled in Springer proceedings	M34
AINIA	Digital solutions for monitoring CO2 emission and capture and the evaluation of other environmental indicators	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	Teledetection conferences	M12-M24
AINIA (in collaboration with Space4Good)	Footprint quantification by teledetection	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers	Scientific journals such as 'Remote sensing'	M24-M36

Table 5: Plan of scientific papers

Regarding the articles in non-academic magazines, the following table shows the topics which are planned to be provided by the partners. A more detailed list will be provided in the next version of the Dissemination & Communication plan. The exact topics and amount of publications can be adapted due to results or progress of the project. They can be written by one or more partners, and the ones initially planned are the following ones. Other ones will follow depending on the results and development of the project:

Lead partner	Topics to be disseminated	Key stakeholder groups and networks
Treedom	Regenerative carbon farming - best practices from the living labs, measuring impact	Policy makers, innovative SMEs, Carbon Credit Buyers, Farmers, Investors, Media
Planet	Carbon Technology Platform	Innovative SMEs, Carbon Credit buyers, Investors, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems
Circonnect	Regenerative Carbon farming - the new sustainable way of carbon farming	Environmental Agencies & NGOs, Farmers, Media, Carbon Credit Buyers, Carbon Credit Verifiers & Brokers
AB Corporation	Business models for carbon farming	Innovative SMEs, Carbon Credit buyers, Investors, Farmers, Business & Sustainability Clusters

Table 6: Plan of articles to be published

4.2.2 Presentation at scientific conferences/practitioner events

Between M4 to M36, INNO4CFIs partners will actively participate at minimum five events, as well as in minimum three panel sessions & three symposia. These engagements will involve a diverse range of activities, including oral presentations, panels, and workshops. The focus will revolve around four pivotal thematic areas: Carbon Credits, Carbon Farming, Climate, and Sustainability; Agriculture and Circular Economy; Satellite Technologies and AI. By actively contributing and participating in these events, it is aimed to disseminate the project's knowledge, exchange insights with peers, and bolster the project's visibility and impact within these crucial domains.

INNO4CFIs plans to disseminate the results at scientific conferences:

Partner	Potential topics to be disseminated	Key stakeholder groups and networks	Means of dissemination
Planet	Mangrove Technology Platform and Incubator	Innovation & Technology ecosystems, Innovative SMEs	Will be defined

Novobiom	Mycelium based solutions, Soil C storage, Mycomaterial enhancing plant growth	Innovation & Technology ecosystems, Innovative SMEs	Will be defined
Space4Good	Defining & observing places for Carbon Farming	Farmers, Innovative SMEs, Investors, Carbon Credit Buyers	Will be defined
Treedom	Applicability in Living Labs, Integration on Tree Planting Platforms	Farmers, Media, Municipalities, Environmental Agencies & NGOs	Will be defined
F6S/AINA	Greentech markets	Innovative SMEs, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems	Will be defined
USAL	Blockchain & AI for carbon farming	Carbon Credit Verifiers & Brokers, Policy makers, Carbon Credit Buyers	International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence (DCAI)
CNR	Measuring the performance of Carbon Farming in Agroforestry system	Universities & Research institutes, Policy makers, Farmers, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems	Poster or Presentation to 1° Forum Nazionale di Agroforestazione . 6-7 DICEMBRE 2023 . Rome, IT 7th European Agroforestry Conference . 27 – 31 MAY 2024 . Brno, CZ

Fondazione E. Amaldi	Space Technology for regenerative carbon farming	Innovative SMEs, Academia, Investors	Paper presentation @International Astronautical Conference 2024 - Milan
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Table 7: Plan of dissemination in scientific conferences

INNO4CFIs presents the results and carbon farming solutions at the following practitioners' events and will interact with stakeholder groups:

Partner	Topics to be disseminated	Key stakeholder groups and networks	Means of dissemination
FEA	Innovation and technologies of CFI technologies and potential application	Policy makers, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Business & Sustainability Clusters	IAC 2024
Circonnect	Focus on regenerative and nature-based solutions, Circular Economy	Business & Sustainability Clusters, Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Environmental Agencies & NGOs, Farmers, Media,	e.g. Climate Lab Vienna Event 2024
Treedom	Good practices from Living labs and Integration in existing platforms, systems of compensation	Innovative SMEs, Carbon Credit buyers, Investors, Farmers,	The conference/event will be defined.
Rancho	Perspective of farmers	Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Policy makers, Farmers, Municipalities	The conference/event will be defined.

Planet	Technology & NBS for Carbon Farming	Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Policy makers, Farmers, Municipalities	The conference/event will be defined.
Space4Good	Satellite Technology for Carbon Farming	Innovation & Technology Ecosystems, Policy makers, Farmers, Municipalities	The conference/event will be defined.

Table 8: Plan for presentations at practitioner events

5 Internal communication

The internal communication in the consortium will be coordinated by the Project Coordinator, to get updates on the progress of the work of each partner as well as ensuring the collaboration of the partners. This will be outlined in the Project Management Plan.

In order to ensure that the results of INNO4CFIs are communicated well to external audiences as well as that all relevant results and activities are communicated via INNO4CIFS communication channels, an **Ambassador concept** is developed. Each partner of the consortium identified the person responsible for communication, the INNO4CFIs (Communication) Ambassador. The ambassadors are nodal points and catalysts to promote INNO4CFIs. The Ambassador will inform the leader of WP10 and execute the dissemination and communication of the partner to its own network in alignment with the central communication function. Furthermore, they share updates, results and news that need to be communicated to Circonnect.

This ensures a smooth interaction between the partners and achieves alignment in the messages provided to the target audiences. In regular meetings (planned on a monthly basis as part of the consortium meeting) the ambassadors will align on dissemination & communication activities, provide the latest news which could be of interest to the stakeholders and target audiences, and clarify which support is needed in crafting messages. Presentations at conferences and international events will be coordinated. As each partner has their own network they can identify where another consortium partner may contribute to online events as speakers to spread the idea of INNO4CFIs topics.

To boost knowledge and skills sharing among partners, at the beginning of the project three internal workshops are organised.

Partner	Topic	Description
Space4Good	GIS and Remote Sensing	This workshop dives into the basics of geo-spatial data and accessible operations for data handling. We also explore the realm of satellites and how to monitor and analyse their data with optical remote sensing procedures. During the workshop we explored Vector and raster data types, Coordinate Reference systems, Basic GIS processing tools & operations. To the participants Space4Good applications and platforms were showcased.
USAL	Distributed Ledger Technologies	This workshop delves into the intricate world of DLTs, exploring aspects like Peer-to-Peer (P2P) networks, cryptographic practices in blockchain, and the fundamentals of digital currencies like Bitcoin as an example to explain the technology. We'll delve into Ethereum and its functionalities, particularly focusing on the Ethereum Virtual Machine and its role in running smart contracts. Moreover, we'll explore digital identity, the crucial role of oracles in blockchains, and introduce Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) to understand their advantages and future applications.
USAL	Decentralised Voluntary Carbon Markets	This workshop offers a detailed exploration of decentralised voluntary carbon markets. Starting with an introduction into carbon offsets and voluntary carbon markets, we will explore the intersection of Digital Ledger Technologies (specifically Ethereum) with carbon offsets, offering transparency and traceability. The workshop will examine the emergent world of decentralised finance (DeFi), its relevance, challenges, and its interplay with carbon markets. Additionally, it will provide insight into the EU's proposal for certification for carbon removals and delve deep into the aspects that encapsulate certification frameworks, regulatory compliance, and oversight mechanisms for carbon removals.

Table 9: Internal workshops

6 Sustainability strategy

To ensure the sustainability of INNO4CFIs and the Carbon Technology Platform beyond project lifetime, INNO4CFIs develops and implements a sustainability strategy. This

comprises the stakeholder engagement plan including project network database, interactive workshops, the clustering and partnerships and the policy uptake. The sustainability strategy is **bottom-up and top-down** at the same time and both are required for a successful exploitation of the project. Bottom-up activities are done by developing the Carbon Technology Platform, local living labs and stakeholder engagement. Top-down activities include ensuring the right legal framework conditions.

6.1 Stakeholder engagement plan

Based on the stakeholder analysis and mapping the way how INNO4CFIs will involve the stakeholders has been developed. The main perspective of the engagement is to achieve that more regenerative carbon farming solutions are being implemented. When working with the stakeholders it is important to clarify how INNO4CFIs will contribute to achieving that and what the impact will be.

6.1.1 Purpose of stakeholder engagement

The stakeholder engagement is the key to the sustainability of the project. Only by the right way of stakeholder engagement, INNO4CFIs and the Carbon Technology platform will be interesting for decision makers and taken up by the market. Stakeholders can support the market uptake by access to policy implementation, access to potential users, access to funding, access to sustainable solutions and the dissemination via their channels as shown in the Stakeholder analysis.

6.1.2 Stakeholder engagement strategy

The aim of the Stakeholder engagement strategy is to address, engage with multiple stakeholders in an effective way. This strategy will be evaluated and further developed throughout the project based on the development of the INNO4CFIs product and clustering strategy.

For the stakeholder engagement including dissemination and communication INNO4CFIs runs a **multi-level-approach (see figure below)**. The multi-level-approach includes engaging stakeholders in the following ways:

- One-way communication: Messages reach the audience via INNO4CFIs official channels or a partner. The stakeholder is informed.
- Two-way interaction: Messages are directed to the audience and the receiver sends feedback to INNO4CFIs.

- Network communication: This is an ecosystemic approach to activate networks and spread the message broadly. All partners are engaging stakeholders from their own network directly, however, to ensure the consortium messages are aligned, a central information hub will be provided by Circonnect who is coordinating WP10. Furthermore, the communication is shared with stakeholders and cluster partners who share INNO4CFIs information with their networks. Clear communication guidelines ensure that the messaging is consistent and represents INNO4CFIs products and findings in an accurate way.

To define the ways on how to engage stakeholders, the [Stakeholder Survey](#) collected views of the project partners about

- The information needs: What are the stakeholder groups interested in?
- Priorities for interaction: What are the main priorities on how to interact with this stakeholder group?
- How can the stakeholder groups support INNO4CFIs to establish itself on the market?

The bold texts are the ones with highest priorities. While a lot of stakeholder groups are seen as partners for the implementation during the project, there are some groups which are crucial for the uptake on the market. During the stakeholder workshop individual contacts within the stakeholder groups have been identified.

Stakeholder Group	Information Needs	Priorities for interaction	How can they help on market uptake?
Carbon Credit Verifiers & Brokers	Carbon Farming solutions, Carbon Credit system	Network partners , obtaining information	Access to potential users
Companies / Carbon Credit Buyers	Carbon Credit systems , Business Opportunities, Carbon Farming solutions	Network partners , gain market acceptance	Access to potential users
Policy makers	Climate Adaptation , Carbon Farming solutions, Gaining knowledge, Innovation & Technology	Obtaining information, getting support	Access to policy implementation , Communicate in their channels
Inno& Tech Ecosystems	Innovation & Technology	Network partners, Spread ideas & solutions,	Use their network to establish solutions , Communicate in their channels
Business & Sustainability Clusters	Collaboration & Network , Business Opportunities, Innovation & Technology	Network partners, Spread ideas & solutions	Access to potential users , use their network to establish solutions
I3 & European programs	Collaboration & Network , Gaining Knowledge	Co-creation & knowledge sharing	Communicate in their channels
Innovative SMEs	Collaboration & Network , Business Opportunities	Co-creation & knowledge sharing , spread ideas & solutions, Increasing understanding, Gain market acceptance	Use their network to establish solutions
Farmers	Business Opportunities, Climate Adaptation	Increasing understanding, Gain market acceptance, Obtaining information, Co-creation & knowledge sharing,	Access to potential users

		spread ideas & solutions	
Investors	Business Opportunities, Carbon Credit Systems	Gain market acceptance, getting support	Access to funding / financial resources
Environmental Agencies & NGOs	Gaining Knowledge, Climate Adaptation, Collaboration & Network	Spread ideas & solutions, Obtaining information	Communicate in their channels, Use their network to establish solutions
Universities & Research Institutes	Gaining Knowledge, Innovation & Technology, Collaboration & Network	Co-creation & knowledge sharing, Increasing understanding, obtaining information	Use their network to establish solutions, Communicate in their channels
Media	Collaboration & Network, Gaining Knowledge	Spread ideas & solutions	Communicate in their channels
Municipalities	Collaboration & Network	Increasing understanding, co-creation & knowledge sharing	Access to policy implementation

Table 10: Engagement strategies for INNO4CFIs stakeholder groups

From a geographical perspective the focus of the engagement lies in the countries where the consortium partners operate. However, when identifying opportunities for future living labs and a wider implementation, further regions in Europe may be integrated. The focus of the INNO4CFIs project will be to establish solutions to be implemented in Europe, even though potential for carbon farming and capturing emissions may be higher in the southern hemisphere. The need of companies to identify local and verifiable solutions to offset their carbon emissions is taken into account when developing the INNO4CFIs technology and platform.

As the weather conditions in Europe will change due to climate change, the solutions of INNO4CFIs in addition can show a way forward on the Carbon Farming sector when operating under difficult circumstances like arid land, water scarcity or toxic soil, as well as the need of local farmers to develop solutions for more resilience.

6.1.3 Stakeholder Engagement Planning

It becomes clear that a dedicated plan for addressing the information needs of the stakeholders is a crucial success factor of bringing the solutions to the market. Based on the stakeholder survey and the stakeholder workshop some key activities for engagement have been identified which will be pursued throughout the project:

- Establish networks with actors in the Carbon Credit system
- Gain an understanding how to showcase the benefits of regenerative carbon farming models to Policy makers, Investors and NGOs
- Engage with Cluster organisations on Business & Sustainability, Innovation & Technology via partners who already have a working relationship
- Build a connection to Policy makers especially on European and national level using the EU network
- Establish connections with partners from other I3 projects.
- Focus on the regions where consortium partners are based when addressing

The stakeholders will be engaged via the following tools shown in the communication matrix below.

6.1.4 Communication matrix

In order to implement the stakeholder engagement strategy, INNO4CFIs develops the instruments project network database and interactive workshops throughout the project.

Stakeholder group	Example organisation	Main ways to addressing them
ENABLERS		
Policy makers on EU, national and regional level	European Commission European Parliament EARSC, Expert Group on Carbon Farming Methodologies National and regional Policy makers in Greece, Italy, Spain, Belgium as well as the	Website Publications Video Conferences & events Press releases Newsletters Social media Stakeholder consultation Policy briefs

	Netherlands, Germany, Austria, Ireland.	
Municipalities	Municipalities in the living labs: Spain, Italy, Greece and Belgium	Website Living Labs Publications Video Press releases Meetings in Person Policy briefs
Environmental agencies & NGOs	European and national (e.g. Italian and Greece) NGOs focused on Climate & environmental aspects Network of S4G AIAF, SISEF (ecology, sylviculture, Agroforestry) ICOS (Irish cooperative organisation) Economy for the Common Good	Website Scientific publications Publications Video Conferences & events Press releases Newsletters Social media Stakeholder consultation
Innovation & Technology Ecosystems	F6S, Start-up, Incubator and Accelerator programs of universities, Impact Hub Community Climate Lab Austria	Website Scientific publications Publications Conferences & events Interactive workshops Press releases Newsletters Social media Network events
IMPLEMENTERS		
Innovative SMEs	Planet, TreeO, Novobiom, Space4Good, Treedom F6S platform partners Partners of FEA, Circonnect,	Website Publications Network Events Conferences & events

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive workshops Cascade Funding Newsletters Social media Network Events of Partners
Companies / Carbon Credit Buyers	Partners of Treedom, TreeO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Publications Conferences & events Interactive workshops Press releases Social media Stakeholder consultation
Farmers and agricultural communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rancho Local Farmers in Italy and Greece Partners of Treedom 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Living Lab visits Conferences & events Specialised workshops Newsletters Social media Stakeholder consultation
Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business Angels Network, Impact Investors Cooperative Bank of Karditsa 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Publications Conferences & events Interactive workshops Social media Stakeholder consultation
Carbon Credit Verifiers & Brokers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon Standards International Carbon markets experts Carbon Future PEFC Italia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications Publications Conferences & events Interactive workshops Press releases Direct interaction Social media Stakeholder consultation
MULTIPLIERS		

Business & Sustainability Clusters	European Business Network (BNI) BCorp Network, Enterprise Europe Network, Rete Clima Social Entrepreneurship Networks Circular Economy Club Cluster on Sustainability transition Greece	Website Publications Video Conferences & events Network Events Newsletters Social media Stakeholder consultation
I3 & European programs	I3 Cohorts European projects partners are already involved, Urban Innovation Actions Life Project C.Farms Circular Bioeconomy Europe CARDIMED Horizon Europe	Website Scientific publications Publications Conferences & events Press releases Newsletters Social media Direct contact Cluster Events
Universities & Research Institutes	Technical University of Athens, University of Salamanca, CNR Further Universities with relevant research topics	Scientific publications Publications Scientific Conferences & events Online research Specialised workshops Newsletters Social media Stakeholder consultation
Media	Media partners of consortium members	Website Publications Video Conferences & events Press releases Newsletters Social media

Table 11: Communication Matrix

6.1.5 Project network database

The project network database is a tool to collect stakeholder contacts of the INNO4CFIs projects including relevant contacts by the consortium partners. The purpose is to identify concrete stakeholder contacts amongst the consortium and of the project. It shows for which stakeholder groups and in which countries there is a good network available. And it shows the gaps of the stakeholders. The contacts will be approached by the contact owners on a personal basis for specific topics and to be invited to subscribe to the INNO4CFIs newsletter or other communication channels. Only if stakeholders subscribe to the INNO4CFIs updates, they will receive mailings. This procedure ensures the alignment with the GDPR regulation.

Currently, the database holds 180 contacts from all stakeholder groups. There are gaps to be filled in the fields of carbon credit buyers. The database will be continuously updated throughout the project.

6.1.6 Interactive workshops

The project will coordinate interactive workshops to engage stakeholders on topics related to the INNO4CFIs development. These workshops will be held by one or more members of the consortium and will be facilitated by Circonnect.

In order to reach the different target groups, the following three interactive workshops are planned. The participants should be stakeholders from outside the consortium which have been identified as key to bring the solutions to the market. The workshops foreseen are:

1. Online: Workshop with the chosen green tech solution providers of the Cascade Funding will be organised between M22 and M30 (timing will be aligned with the cascade funding and can change). This will ensure the solution providers get to know each other and the partners of the INNO4CFIs project, and enable a better understanding of the solutions and identifying collaboration opportunities. It is planned to be after the beneficiaries for the Cascade Funding have been chosen.
2. Collaborative workshop with a similar initiative and/or other I3-/EU-funded project(s): INNO4CFIs will organise at least one collaborative workshop with other I3 and/or EU-funded projects and similar initiatives. This will foster the clustering and collaboration with stakeholders with similar interests. The collaboration

allows to engage a broad audience of key audiences, fosters dissemination and exploitation of the project. It will be organised between M12 and M30.

3. Online/hybrid/in-presence: Workshop with the focus on integrating the regenerative Carbon Farming models to the Carbon Credit system, identifying business models and potential investors. This workshop will be planned between M31 and M34 in the context of a major conference on the topic, e.g. the World Circular Economy Forum, to achieve visibility and an international audience of potential investors and implementers of the solutions.

Furthermore, a special session/workshop will be organised by the INNO4CFIs consortium, led by USAL in the framework of the [International Conference on Distributed Computing and Artificial Intelligence](#) (DCAI). This session will be devoted to the project topics and be celebrated annually, where partners will have the opportunity to share the progress of the project and the main outcomes with an academic audience (mainly). The scientific papers submitted to the conference will be compiled in Springer proceedings.

6.2 Clustering & Partnerships

6.2.1 Clustering & Partnerships strategy

A key element of the sustainability strategy is clustering. **Clustering** means to develop a **network of partners (including companies, organisations, EU initiatives, innovative SMEs or similar)** who are interested in becoming part of the INNO4CFIs Carbon Technology platform, applying the technologies and/or contributing to the development of the carbon farming technology and network. The aim is to develop **at least five MoUs** by the end of the project that demonstrate the interest in replicating or transferring the technology. By that, the adaptation, market uptake and exploitation in one of the INNO4CFIs regions or other regions will be ensured. The communication and stakeholder engagement strategy is developed to engage the target audiences and develop strong relationships that are the basis of the clustering. Therefore, this activity is ongoing from M1 to M36.

The clustering and partnership strategy includes developing strong partnerships with other **I3-, PRIMA, Horizon Europe or ERDF-**projects. This can include a common dissemination and communication in case of overlapping topics to reach a broader audience. It is also important to develop strong relationships at regional level and develop **local contact points** in INNO4CFIs key regions. Furthermore, the collaboration with **carbon credit systems**

(Carbon credit-verifiers and -buyers) is essential for the market research, identifying market needs and enabling the market uptake of INNO4CFIS.

6.2.2 Task Force Clustering & Market uptake

One of the aims of the INNO4CFIs project is to develop a business model of INNO4CFIs in the field of nature-based solutions and carbon farming. The objective is that INNO4CFIs has a **strong clustering network** and transferable cases in Europe and world-wide. Ideally, a **sustainable business model** for the platform is established after three years or in a good development in that direction.

To develop a strong clustering network and a sustainable business model expertise from partners, a good collaboration and exchange across the work packages is needed. Therefore, INNO4CFIs establishes the **Taskforce Clustering & Market uptake** as from M13 dedicated to the market uptake and sustainability of the project that meets every six weeks. The taskforce consists of the following partners: Planet, Fondazione E. Amaldi, AB Corporation, Treedom, Space4Good, Circonnect, F6S, Treeo, Novobiom. The taskforce is facilitated by Circonnect, and the content is led by AB Corporation as the work package lead of the strongly related topics of Business modelling and other stakeholder engagement tasks in the context of WP9.

The aim of the taskforce is to:

1. Promote the Clustering: It is essential that the technology maturation, business model, outcomes of the living labs is aligned with the clustering activities that include all communication and stakeholder engagement activities.. Only by that a market oriented platform and product will be developed.
2. Attract the right actors for the cascade funding which will be the basis of the replication and transferability cases of the project.
3. Develop a business model for the INNO4CFIs Carbon Technology Platform. This includes market research, interacting with carbon credit buyers and other key stakeholders and developing a product that is attractive for the market.

The continuous work of the Taskforce Clustering & Partnerships starts in M13 up to M36 and is a crucial part of the sustainability and exploitation strategy.

6.3 Policy uptake

Essential for the exploitation and market uptake of the Carbon Technology platform are the right legal conditions that enable a business case for technology providers and farmers. Based on the results of the research on the legal framework conditions undertaken in WP8, a minimum of 1 policy brief will be developed between M24 and M36. The aim is to reach out to European policy makers and regional policymakers with a focus on the regions of the project's living labs and raise awareness about the importance of regenerative carbon farming in European regions referring to the Carbon Removal Certification, Farm2Fork strategy, the Green Deal and Common agricultural policy. The aim is to show current legal gaps that are hindering the implementation and suggest solutions.

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

Communication activities need an ongoing evaluation and improvement. For INNO4CFIs, 2 ways of monitoring and evaluation are differentiated.

1. Tracking the KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities
2. Active and regenerative stakeholder engagement

The first topic ensures meeting the objectives set in the Grant Agreement which will provide a high visibility of the project, its partners and the solutions developed.

The regenerative model ensures that the fast-evolving system of Carbon Farming is addressed in an agile way that offers resilience and high adaptability of the project.

7.1 Tracking the communication and dissemination activities

To achieve the KPIs, a regular measurement regarding the external communication activities will take place. INNO4CFIs will measure via digital tools and regularly collect information by consortium partners via the Dissemination and Communication Form. At the dates mentioned, an update of the actual situation will be provided to the consortium partners to prepare for the next versions of the Dissemination & Communication Plan.

Media	Measurement criteria
Website	No. of visitors, hits per page, references on other pages
LinkedIn Page	No. of followers, no. of impressions and views per post
X-Account (Twitter)	No. of tweets, no. of views per promoted post
YouTube	No. of followers, no. videos, no. of views
Press releases	2 press releases planned, no. of media partners reached
Newsletters	No. of editions, no. of people reached
Peer-reviewed articles	3 articles planned, no. of articles entered for peer-review
Journal / Magazine articles	No. of articles, magazine news, reach of journals
Panel sessions & Symposia	No. of panel sessions, symposia, participants
Presentations Practitioner Events	No. of presentations, no. of people reached
Communication activities of partners	No. of participation in events, no. of workshops organised, no. of people reached in practitioner events and conferences
Interactive workshops	3 workshops planned - no. of participants per workshop

Table 12: Tracking communication & dissemination activities

In addition, partners will update the communication & dissemination activities they have planned on a regular basis. This will be reflected in future versions of the Dissemination & Communication Plan at M12, M24 and M36.

7.2 Continuous evaluation and regenerative stakeholder engagement

The Stakeholder engagement strategy and plan will be evaluated at M10, M22 and M34. For the evaluation a regenerative and agile model will be used as this fits best to the complex environment the project is operating in and ensures resilience and fast adaptability.

The main objectives in the three phases of the project are:

Phase 1: M1 - M12	Phase 2: M13 - M24	Phase 3: M25 - M36
Create an initial awareness in the regenerative Carbon Farming model	Inform about the opportunities, actions and benefits	Providing tangible results, Gather feedback from participants.
Understand market requirements	Demonstrate early results; Involve new stakeholders	Demonstrate more advanced solutions

While the project partners are developing that Carbon Farming Technology Platform and demonstrating it in the living labs, it is essential to consider that INNO4CFIs is working with living ecosystems that are constantly changing. The solutions from INNO4CFIs will change the systems, new stakeholders will emerge as well as new technology solutions, and the new partners based on the Cascade Funding will need to be integrated as well. This living ecosystem requires a more agile, active and reflective approach of stakeholder engagement which will allow INNO4CFIs to adapt fast to changes and provide resilience. At each of the General Assemblies, it is foreseen to have a lessons learned workshop focusing on stakeholder engagement and how it can be developed further.

This showcases that the regenerative models are not just applied in the design of the Carbon Farming models the consortium develops, but also in the way the collaboration with stakeholders in the consortium as well as outside the consortium is being developed. The Carbon Farming ecosystem and environment is growing while the project is ongoing. In 2023, according to the [Stockholm Resilience Center](#), 6 of the planetary boundaries that regulate the stability and resilience of the Earth system, have been overshoot, so new actors and solutions are emerging to solve these issues. INNO4CFIs addresses 4 of these boundaries directly (Climate Change - CO2 concentration, biosphere integrity, biogeochemical flows, and freshwater change). The project is working within a complex and evolving system. The living systems approach, described by Giles Hutchins in Laura Storm for regenerative businesses drives not only the designs of the solutions, but also the way of engaging stakeholders. Therefore, monitoring and evaluation of the stakeholder engagement and communication activities will happen in cycles and will be adopted to the entire system evolving.

8 References

[EASME 2019, REA 2023](#): Communication, dissemination and exploitation. Why they all matter and what is the difference.

[European Commission, 2010](#): Communicating research for evidence-based policymaking - A practical guide for researchers in socio-economic sciences and humanities. Brussels.

9 Annex

9.1 Visual identity - Brand manual

A brand manual has been developed as a guideline for all partners on how to apply the visuals of INNO4CFIs.

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

BRAND MANUAL

October 2023

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 10115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

1 LOGO

Logo variants

Logo protective space

Logo use

Logo use on backgrounds

Logo placement

2 TYPOGRAPHY

Inter font with
font styles

3 COLORS

Color values print and web

4 DESIGN ELEMENTS

Icons

5 IMAGERY

Possible images to
demonstrate key
messages

LOGO

The central element

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

Primary logo vertical

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Primary logo horizontal

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Primary logo without tagline vertical

INNO4CFIs

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Primary logo without tagline horizontal

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Secondary logo vertical

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Secondary logo horizontal

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Secondary logo without tagline vertical

INNO4CFIs Regenerative Carbon Farming
- G.A. 101115156

Co-funded by
the European Union

Secondary logo without tagline horizontal

Logo protective space

Logo symbol minimum size

Primary logo use

Secondary logo use

Primary logo use on backgrounds

Primary logo use on backgrounds

Primary logo use on backgrounds

Primary logo use on image backgrounds

very light and calm pictures

white logo on calm darker images

white logo on calm darker images

logo on detailed images

logo on dark images

logo on cluttered images

Secondary logo use on backgrounds

Secondary logo use on backgrounds

Primary logo use on backgrounds

Logo placement – Dos

Logo placement – Dos

Logo placement – Don'ts

TYPOGRAPHY

The font in use

INTER REGULAR

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y
Z Ä Ö Ü a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x
y z ä ö ü 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 # @ & \$ = % ? ! %

This is a typo dummy text. Here you can see whether all the letters are there and what they look like. Also you can get a better feeling for the readability.

Aa

INTER MEDIUM

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y
Z Ä Ö Ü a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x
y z ä ö ü 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 # @ & \$ = % ? ! %

This is a typo dummy text. Here you can see whether all the letters are there and what they look like. Also you can get a better feeling for the readability.

Aa

INTER SEMIBOLD

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y
Z Ä Ö Ü a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x
y z ä ö ü 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 # @ & \$ = % ? ! %

This is a typo dummy text. Here you can see whether all the letters are there and what they look like. Also you can get a better feeling for the readability.

Aa

INTER BOLD

A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z
Ä Ö Ü a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z
ä ö ü 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 # @ & \$ = % ? ! %

This is a typo dummy text. Here you can see whether all the letters are there and what they look like. Also you can get a better feeling for the readability.

Aa

COLORS

The color palette at a glance

Primary colors incl. gradations

BLUE

CMYK 70 | 22 | 7 | 0 RGB 67 | 160 | 208 HEX #43A0D0

CMYK 52 | 13 | 3 | 0 RGB 130 | 188 | 228 HEX #82BCE4 **80% Opacity**

CMYK 39 | 8 | 2 | 0 RGB 165 | 207 | 237 HEX #A5CFED **60% Opacity**

CMYK 26 | 6 | 2 | 0 RGB 198 | 222 | 242 HEX #C6DEF2 **40% Opacity**

CMYK 13 | 4 | 3 | 0 RGB 228 | 237 | 245 HEX #E4EDF5 **20% Opacity**

GREEN

CMYK 63 | 0 | 78 | 0 RGB 105 | 183 | 94 HEX #69B75E

CMYK 45 | 1 | 61 | 0 RGB 159 | 202 | 130 HEX #9FCA82 **80% Opacity**

CMYK 33 | 2 | 41 | 0 RGB 187 | 215 | 172 HEX #BBD7AC **60% Opacity**

CMYK 22 | 2 | 26 | 0 RGB 211 | 228 | 203 HEX #D3E4CB **40% Opacity**

CMYK 10 | 2 | 10 | 0 RGB 235 | 242 | 235 HEX #EBF2EB **20% Opacity**

Secondary colors

DARKER BLUE

CMYK 70 | 22 | 7 | 50 RGB 42 | 100 | 129 HEX #2A6481

YELLOW

CMYK 6 | 23 | 89 | 0 RGB 242 | 195 | 41 HEX #F2C329

MUTED ROSE

CMYK 13 | 76 | 32 | 2 RGB 212 | 91 | 122 HEX #D45B7A

4

DESIGN ELEMENTS

The other design assets

Use of pictograms/icons

IMAGERY

Images to demonstrate key messages

Images for keywords “Green technology”, “Nature and technology” and “Biodiversity”

Images to demonstrate “carbon farming” and “nature-based solutions”

Images to demonstrate “carbon farming” and “nature-based solutions”

9.2 Templates

PowerPoint

Word - Report template

Table Style 2

DELIVERABLE 10.1	COMMUNICATION STRATEGY
Related Work Package	Stet cilita kasd gubergren
Deliverable lead	Lorem ipsum dolor
Author(s)	Stet cilita kasd gubergren Stet cilita kasd gubergren Stet cilita kasd gubergren
Contact	lorem@ipsum.com
Reviewer	Stet cilita kasd
Grant Agreement Number	0123456
Funding body	Dolore magna aliquyam
Start date	01. Nov 2023
Project Duration	24 months
Type of Delivery (R, DEM, DEC, Other)1	R = Report
Dissemination Level (PU, CO, C)2	PU = Public
Date Last update	15.03.2024
Approved by	Lorem ipsum
Website	www.inno4cfis.eu

Table Style 3

D 10.1	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur	M1 - M3	Jan 2024
D 10.2	Nonummy eirmod tempor	M4	Feb 2024
D 10.3	At vero et accusam	M7	Mar 2024

9.3 Timeline

9.3.1 Timeline: Task 10.1 M1-12

9.3.2 Timeline: Task 10.2 M1-12

